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Abstract: In brief about Avloni, he has been creating for more than 30 years. He registered labor occasions of 1916 followed by revolutionary upheavals and national liberational problems. In the past, he said he had “left dozens of poems and school books, four theatre books”. When talking about his role in our history of our culture, we should emphasize two aspects: pedagogical activity and literary art. His pedagogical activity and ideas about education are really crucial source of defining the features of awareness which rose a new level in twentieth century. In the article we will observe such facilities as his pedagogical activity, hid educative behaviour, his call to science, his engagement the goodness and intelligence.

Keywords: Education, pedagogy, science, researches, the Avloni school, knowledge, culture, society, intelligence, intellect, mind, nation, description, idea.

Abdulla Avloniy, a renowned sophisticated writer and a great spokesperson of Jadid movement, had a considerable contribution to the improvement of pedagogical knowledge. Abdulla Avloni was born on July 12th 1878 in Mergancha neighborhood of Tashkent in a family of small craftsmen. When he was 7 he studied in an old school. Akramhon domla taught him. In 1890 he began to study in the medrassah in Mergancha. Then mullah Omar Ohun taught him at Abdumalikboy's madrassah. He was interested in literature. He entered a madrassa at the age of 12 after graduating an old methodical school. He worked in summer which helped his farther and mother, also studied in his free time.

Abdulla Avloniy had ability and aspiration to create new thing in term of literature. His first poem and article was Hijran, motivate individuals to study at school with the aid of new method and to think independently. He began publishing a newspaper called Shukhrat, Azia in 1907, however the officials of the Tsarist Russia found it easily. Abdullah Avloni later worked as an editor was busy with creative and practical work. He wrote his poems under the penname «Hijron». His articles were published under the hames «Mulla Abdulla», «Avloni», «Abdulla Avloni». Later he mostly used the nickname «Indamas» (Silent) in the newspapers Sadoyi Turkiston (1914-1915), Turan (1917), Participation (1918), and the Journal of the Homework Movement. After that, he became known as one of the founders of the Uzbek press. Abdulla Avloni was conscious of the great role of newspapers and magazines in spreading progressive ideas among the people and in promoting science and insight. In 1907, he published Shuhrat, an Asian newspaper, and edited it. In the first issue of the newspaper, thinking about the place of the press, the role of the newspaper, the mass media says that it is challenging for a fish to live without water. Abdulla Avloni played a vital place in the development of pedagogical ideas in the socio-political life of Uzbekistan in the early twentieth century. Abdulla Avloni is a writer, public figure and talented pedagogue who has made a significant contribution to the progress of art and literature of the Uzbek people, as well as national culture and public education. Turan theater troupe. However, there were major hinderance for the troupe to become a professional theater. The colonial policy of the tsarist government was against all forms of theater that helped to awaken the social consciousness of the people. In this time when the theater had such a negative attitude, Avloni's organization of a theatrical troupe and staging of social plays was a considerable courage for his enlightenment.

In 1909 he founded «Jamiyati Hayriya» the collected and distributed finance to give knowledge regional children. At the end of 1913 the society «Turon» was founded through the self-

motivation of prominent Tashkent Jadids, maintenances of development. One of the responsible person was Avloni Theatre army was founded under the community. The first play which was staged by the troop was «Padarkush» by Behbudi. Avloni wrote plays namely «Advokatlik osonmi», (Is it easy to be the lawyer), «Pinak», «Biz va siz» (We and you), «Ikki sevgi» (Two loves), «Portugaliya Inqilobi» (Portuguese revolution) for the troop. Plays like «Kotili karima», «Uy tarbiyasining bir shakli», «Hiyonatkor oilasi», «Badbaxt kelin», «Hor-hor», «Jaholat», «O'liklar» were translated into tartar, azerbaijan. Avloni published the newspaper «Turon» with (under) the motto «Yashasin Halq Jamiyati!» after the February events in 1917.

Avloni school was constructed on the support of humanistic and free education, with the major task of giving children secular and advanced science, and ensuring that young people have the ability to participate in the socio-political life of the country. The author compiled textbooks for these schools. His first teacher, *The First Teacher* (1911), was reprinted four times before the October Revolution, and his post-alphabetic textbook, *The Second Teacher* (1912), three times. The textbook «*Turkish Gulistan or Morality*» (1913) with a moral didactic content played a special role in the development of socio-pedagogical thought in the early twentieth century. It first examines the problems of education and ethics in terms of the requirements and needs of the twentieth century. While Avloni differentiates between traditional good and bad behavior, he approves his views on the ideas of Hippocrates, Plato, Aristotle, Saadi Sherazi, and Bedil, and uses modernity as the principal category. The writer considered the love of the Motherland to be one of the best human virtues to fight for. Homeland is the city and country where everyone is born and grew. He needs to be respected, loved, rejuvenated. The poet understood this when he said *Vatan* and love for it. The love of language and culture is the love of each person for his people: “The mirror life of every nation is the language and literature that demonstrate its existence in the world. The loss of the national language is the loss of the spirit of the nation. It should be noted that Avloni went through a very difficult life and career. He entered the literature at a time when ideological struggles were in full swing. He unhesitatingly embraced the struggle for enlightenment and progress. As you become acquainted with the poetry of the poet, you will encounter an interesting situation. There are no romantic poems in it. He knows social problems and people's worries more important. He denies any love in the face of the misfortune of the People and the Homeland. He «loves his mother like a friend.» He dedicates all his love to it.

In the starting of the century was a time of main responsibility for the fate of Turkestan, when the problem of its life and death was being found a solutions. He was a leading intellectual of the Avloni period, a great enlightener, and an active supporter of the teachings of the Jadids. 1917) and in his *tazkira* «*Sabzavor*» (1914) and in the periodicals.

They promote knowledge, and ignorance, criticise the socio-moral foundations of the old system, and spoke of a free and happy time. In this sense, Avloni's poems of this period are in tune with the poetry of Hamza and Anbar Atin. Avloni used finger weights extensively in the literature. He wrote poems to national melodies and enriched the possibilities of poetry.

The most significant his contributions for our literature was modern phenomenon called Labor poetry. He wrote poems describing the events of 1916, such as «The words of a laborer's father to his son,» «The mother's words to her son,» and «Sorry.» The motherland brightened the valediction divisions of the laborers who had been taken to the snowy and icy lands of the far north, to the blueworkers behind the front, to unfairness. The melody and style of these poems were very close to folk songs, which played an crucial role in the national awakening of our people.

In conclusion, Abdulla Avloni was a prominent, enlightened and brilliant example of the Jadid movement.

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